

EFFECT OF ECOLITERACY AND GENDER BASED ON CONTRIBUTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION

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Abstract

Ecoliteracy is a knowledge and understanding of the environment accompanied by relevant behavior in accordance with the level of understanding possessed by a person. The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of ecoliteracy and gender on the contribution of environmental conservation of Biology Education students in Universitas Negeri Jakarta. The study used ex post facto method with 2 x 2 factorial design. The technique of data collection began with the test of ecoliteracy. The technique of data analysis used two-ways ANOVA. The results show that the contribution of students who have high ecoliteracy higher than the group of students who have low ecoliteracy. Thus, ecoliteracy positively influences the contribution of environmental conservation also there is difference in the contribution of environmental conservation to male and female, but there is no interaction between ecoliteracy and gender toward the contribution of environmental conservation.

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1. Introduction

Environmental concerns have come under scrutiny since the UN Conference on the Environment in Stockholm, Sweden, on 15 June 1972. After this conference, environmental concerns have begun to become the world's attention (Panteghini and Sandberg, 2015). In Indonesia, environmental problems are preceded by the implementation of Environmental Education in various educational institutions (Nomura, 2009). One of the first educational institutions to organize learning environment education is the Jakarta Institute of Teacher Training (IKIP) which is currently known as the Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

Universitas Negeri Jakarta (UNJ) is the forerunner of the organizer of Environmental Education in higher education level. The cultivation of the concept of environmental education in UNJ since 1991 is certainly based on the expectation that students have high sensitivity and concern for the surrounding environment, both the campus environment and the environment in which they live. The reality on the ground shows that until now the UNJ campus environment is still far from the word clean. Every day there are a number of garbage piles, not infrequently can be found students who throw the garbage is not in place. Even when it rains, some areas of the campus are inundated. The problem in this field shows that environmental education that has been given to students for years has not had any real impact. The purpose of environmental education is to make students think comprehensively. Environmental education also leads to a sense of care to the environment and the sense of responsibility for the environment in order to still be enjoyed by the next generation in a sustainable manner. In this case, the entire campus academic community has the same contribution to maintain the cleanliness and hygiene of the campus. Including the lecturers, students, employees, until the janitor, both men, and women. From another perspective, gender can be interpreted as the differences between men and women in terms of values and behavior in social life (Setiawan, Budiantara and Ratnasari, 2017). The differences between men and women in the biological aspect are always used to define rights, roles, and functions within society.

Ecoliteracy or knowledge of the environment of each gender can influence the way of view and the mindset in judging something. This viewpoint that can affect the mindset of a person, in this

study of male and female students, on attitudes and behavior, one of which is the behavior contribution of environmental conservation. When a student in a campus environment already have attitudes and caring behavior towards the environment, then they will be easier to understand how to address the environmental problems that surround it. Ecoliteracy owned by students can be a benchmark achievement of environmental education courses in the environment of the Universitas Negeri Jakarta. It can also be a consideration of policy making on the importance of environmental education lecture held in each study program.

Environmental education can basically be implemented from a variety of levels, either through formal learning at school (Ramos *et al.*, 2015; Szczytko, Carrier and Stevenson, 2018), non-formal in the community (Kney, Citrin and Clark, 2016), or informally in the family (Stern, Powell and Hill, 2014). At the University level, the problem of environmental pollution is studied only on certain faculties and study program. In the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Universitas Negeri Jakarta, the Biology Education study program has a special subject on Environmental Education. Students can have different ways of thinking about environmental issues by studying the material so that it will affect their contribution of environmental conservation in the community.

The form contribution of environmental conservation shown by the students is basically the result of interaction between various factors namely internal factors and external factors. External factors consist of family, school, and community, while internal factors consist of personality, gender, and sensitivity of each individual to the surrounding issues (Desfandi and Maryani, 2017). In social life, gender is include of the role in the social construction of societies that are not determined by sex, therefore every male and female should have the same rights in social life. But the physical difference makes the society perceive that male have higher degrees in the social life of the community, so both male and female rights should be equal (Ford, 2015; Robinson and Richardson, 2015). There are various ways to view gender development. Some of them focus more on factors in male and female behavior, while others emphasize social or cognitive factors (Semela, 2017).

Based on this background, this study is aimed to find out:

1. The influence of ecoliteracy toward contribution on environmental conservation in Universitas Negeri Jakarta.
2. The influence of gender toward contribution on environmental conservation in Universitas Negeri Jakarta.
3. The interaction between ecoliteracy and gender toward contribution on environmental conservation in Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

So with the ecoliteracy, it can be seen whether there are differences in the contribution of environmental conservation between male and female and also between a student with high and low ecoliteracy at Universitas Negeri Jakarta. If within the students already have an attitude of environmental care and a good understanding of the environment then it is expected to give good results also to the contribution of environmental conservation. Therefore, deep research is needed related to the effect of ecoliteracy and gender on the contribution of environmental conservation.

2. Method

This study use quantitative research paradigm by ex post facto method with the 2x2 factorial design. The location of study is in Universitas Negeri Jakarta. Respondent/data source of this study are 100 students of biology education bachelor program in semester 4 and 6 who have taken environmental education courses in the 3rd semester. Data Collection is done through questionnaire and test. Instrument of ecoliteracy is developed based on core competence of ecoliteracy which is issued by The Center for Ecoliteracy (Panteghini and Sandberg, 2015). Instrument of contribution on environmental conservation is developed based on core competence of participation and contribution which is issued by Xing (Setiawan, Budiantara and Ratnasari,

2017). Variables which are observed in this study are ecoliteracy (X1), gender (X2), and contribution on environmental conservation (Y). Research design such as Table 1.

Table 1. Research Design The Effect of Ecoliteration and Gender on the Contribution of Environmental Conservation.

Attribute Variable		Gender (B)	
		Male (B1)	Female (B2)
Ecoliteracy (A)	High (A1)	A ₁ B ₁	A ₂ B ₁
	Low (A2)	A ₁ B ₂	A ₂ B ₂
Interaction		(A X B)	

3. Results and Discussion

Hypotheses were tested using two-ways analysis of variance (ANOVA). The mechanism of test is done by comparing significance value of calculation result with significance value (probability) of 0.05. The decision taken use criteria “if calculation significance value is < 0.05; then H₀ is rejected”, and “if calculation significance value is > 0.05; then H₀ is accepted.” Hypothesis test is done by IBM SPSS 17 software. Based on the calculation with two-ways ANOVA obtained the result shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	1456.100 ^a	3	485.367	5.254	.004
Intercept	190164.100	1	190164.100	2058.424	.000
Ecoliteracy	435.600	1	435.600	4.715	.037
Gender	1020.100	1	1020.100	11.042	.002
Ecoliteracy * Gender	.400	1	.400	.004	.948
Error	3325.800	36	92.383		
Total	194946.000	40			
Corrected Total	4781.900	39			

a. R Squared = ,305 (Adjusted R Squared = ,247)

3.1. Contribution on environmental conservation in students with high ecoliteracy and low ecoliteracy

The result of a calculation with two-ways ANOVA obtained that the significant number is lower than the alpha; $0.037 < 0.05$. It means the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected and H₁ is accepted. So there is a different contribution of environmental conservation between students with high and low ecoliteracy. Students with high ecoliteracy scored higher than those with low ecoliteracy. An ecologically educated person means one has the ability to make the right decisions and take action to solve the environmental problem (Schimek, 2016). In making decisions and taking appropriate action to solve environmental problems certainly requires special skills. Ecological understanding or ecoliteracy is the ability of a person to read the environmental problems objectively with the head, heart, hand, and soul (Lees, 2017). This contemplative pedagogy can foster the ability to make the right decisions to contribute more to environmental conservation.

Someone with high ecoliteracy is already at the operational level regularly evaluating the impact and taking action aimed at maintaining or improving a healthy environment. Such people demonstrate a strong and sustained sense of investment and responsibility to prevent or restore environmental degradation both personally and collectively, and will likely act at multiple levels

from local to global in doing so (Etmagusti, 2010). Habits characteristic of environmental literacy mind is ingrained. They are regularly involved in dealing with the world at large.

To realize sustainable natural resources and environment management, it is necessary to support the quality of human resources, which can lead to a change in the way of view of the environment with environmental ethics through internalization into production and consumption activities, and to instill environmental values and ethics in daily life includes social learning and formal education from early on (Lees, 2017). The contribution of students and the development of ecoliteracy must be supported by the awareness of within each individual, both in the form of daily experience and in the form of knowledge embedded and applied in everyday life (Saribas, Teksoz and Ertepinar, 2014).

A student with a high ecoliteracy results in high contribution on environmental conservation scores as well. Because in everyday life has applied ecoliteracy in every aspect of life. A person with high ecoliteracy can also contribute to their concern for the environment because of the contribution associated with self-belief. When someone is confident about his or her own environmental knowledge, he or she will act in accordance with the knowledge it has (Carrier, 2009). Therefore, the quality of environmental education and the quality human resources support is needed and should be improved, especially in every study program at Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

3.2. *Contribution on environmental conservation in male and female students*

The result of a calculation with two-ways ANOVA obtained that the significant number is lower than the alpha; $0.002 < 0.05$. It means the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and H_1 is accepted. So there is a different contribution of environmental conservation between male and female students. This finding accordance with the previous research; "Environmental Education articles in Schools: Learning Styles and Genders" which state that boys show greater scores in outdoor treatment groups than in traditional classrooms, boys also get greater scores on attitudes and behaviors than girls. This study suggests that there is a unique learning style of girls and boys and findings (Livesey and Intili, 1996; Johnson *et al.*, 2017; Reilly, Neumann and Andrews, 2017; Ycaza Herrera, Wang and Mather, 2018).

This happens because in this case the researchers differentiate learning styles outdoors and in traditional classrooms, so boys who tend to have higher kinesthetic performance have higher scores than girls. This is consistent with the article Gender Differences in Visual-Spatial Ability in 4-Year-Olds: Effects on Kinesthetic Acuity Task Performance (Poston and Bouvier, 2010). In this article mentioned that the performance of boys is significantly better than girls. According to Poston, gender shows differences that occur in men and women not from a biological point of view (sex) but in social life (Larsen, Randy J.; Buss, David M.; Wismeijer, Andreas; Song, John; van den Berg, 2017). Gender is defined as the rules or norms of behavior associated with gender in a social system of society, which is why gender is often identified with sex or sex, whereas both have different concepts (Wienanda *et al.*, 2017).

Comparisons between male and female show that female tend to reach higher levels of reasoning as well as more coherent reasoning skills. Formal institutions such as schools seem to play a very minimal role in developing students' reasoning (Isdaryanti *et al.*, 2018). Girls' achievements may be related to maturity or personal effort. While teachers as educators suggest that girls tend to focus more on lessons than boys (Widodo, Waldrip and Herawati, 2016).

3.3. *The Effect of Interaction between Ecoliteration and Gender*

The result of a calculation with two-ways ANOVA obtained that the significant number is higher than the alpha; $0.948 > 0.05$. It means the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and H_1 is rejected. So there is no interaction between ecoliteracy and gender to the contribution of environmental conservation. The ecoliteracy of community members depends on varying resources, wealth and gender status. Disadvantaged families will rely heavily on local resources for their livelihoods,

which will have an impact on the contribution of environmental conservation. The role of gender affects both the level and content of individual ecoliteracy. Gender ideology has been measured using many different individual items. The ideology formed on each gender acts as a lens through which individuals perceive their social world. In addition, gender ideology influences one's decisions about education and work (Davis & Greenstein, 2009). There is no interaction between these two variables that both cannot simultaneously affect the contribution of environmental conservation. However, there is a clear relationship between ecoliteracy and environmental education but not significant. This relationship is absolute and is a system of causality (Nomura, 2009). The interaction between ecoliteracy and gender toward contribution of environmental conservation can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Profil Plots Interaction between Ecoliteracy and Gender to The Contribution of Environmental Conservation.

This relationship begins with a sense of concern due to the damages that arise in the environment, environmental problems will cause awareness of the importance of maintaining the environment. The effort begins with awareness through environmental education that shapes the caring character of the environment that will impact on one's contribution to environmental conservation. With the implementation of environmental protection and environmental protection efforts in ecological, economic, and sociological justice simultaneously so that the ultimate goal of a sustainable environment can be realized. So it can be concluded that ecoliteracy and gender effective to improve one's behavior in contributing to preserving the environment but cannot be together with gender in affecting the dependent variable that is the contribution of environmental conservation.

4. Conclusions

There is significant influence of ecoliteracy toward contribution on environmental conservation also there is significant influence of gender toward contribution on environmental conservation. But, there is not significant influence of ecoliteracy and gender toward contribution on environmental conservation. This shows that to achieve the maximal contribution on environmental conservation result, student need environmental education. But it does not matter within gender. There is no difference in contribution on environmental conservation between male and female. This can be accepted because gender not determine someone's contribution. This findings indicate that the contribution on environmental conservation can be formed from the value of ecoliteracy.

5. Suggestions

Taking into account the benefits of environmental understanding to students in the course of environmental education, this course can be applied to other study programs so that it will bring a positive impact for the environment of the State University of Jakarta.

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